

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

ENGR. FLORENCE GALE A. CALIS

Associate Professor 3

Negros Oriental State University

norsu.cea.ee@gmail.com

“LIFE’S INSPIRING TRUTH”

Sunlight peering through the window pane,
Struggling to open my mind, thinking again.
A new day dawns, another chance to celebrate,
Stretch my legs and arms, no time to hesitate.

Before the day starts, a silent prayer I send,
Guide me and keep safe my family, dear friend.
A busy day ahead; I know I must try,
With hope in my heart and my hands held high.

Standing up to get a robe, pondering what’s right,
Little wandering minds await with pure delight.
Getting ready now; time is fleeting here,
I must find my rhythm and let inspiration steer.

So joyful to see those twinkling eyes on me,
It’s evident that it’s worthwhile to choose to be free.
They’ve been waiting for me; I cherish this light
My inspiration and strength; life is brighter with you in sight.